

Gypsum – Hexametaphosphate activation on the hydraulic behaviour of Portland-slag cement

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Abstract : The hydraulic and related properties of Portland-slag cement containing granulated blast furnace slag as high as 40% (w/w) has been examined at room temperature under the mixed activation of gypsum and sodium hexametaphosphate. The study confirmed that the minor dosage of polyelectrolyte, hexametaphosphate with 4% (w/w) gypsum might act as potential activator capable of arresting adverse effect on the physico-chemical properties of high slag-Portland cement composition derived by large scale substitution of cement clinker with blast furnace slag.

Keywords : Portland-blast furnace slag cement, hexametaphosphate activator, hydraulic properties.

Introduction

In the recent years, the effective utilization route of granulated blast furnace slag, a huge industrial waste from iron and steel industries, has been evolved as a supplementary cementitious material through the partial replacement of Portland cement clinker with BF slag which was intimately blended during grinding operation of Portland-slag cement (PSC). The substitution yielded substantial beneficial action in terms of enhancement of durability, low heat of hydration and better sulphate resistance properties. The resultant Portland-slag cement simultaneously created a rather complex environment of slow setting and low early strength development properties since the latent hydraulic behaviour of incorporated blast furnace slag is dependent not only on its chemical and mineralogical composition but also on the type and the glassy phase content in it.

In order to counteract the diversity of BF slag reactivity from different sources and the poor performance behaviour of blended high slag-Portland cement, the proper choice and controlled addition of suitable chemical slag activator has been gaining immense scientific and technological importance that would safely permit maximum percent utilization of granulated blast furnace slag to Portland-slag cement composition.

Available literature on Portland-slag cement distinctly reveals that the nature and dosage of activator plays a crucial role in determining the hydration and strength development characteristics of activated slag cement concrete because activated slag is chemically different from Portland cement clinker and possesses completely different hydration behaviour¹. Some slag activators like calcium hydroxide and gypsum are reported to act as reactant while others like sodium hydroxide and sodium carbonate simply as catalyst. Furthermore, the hydration mechanism of activated slag is largely related to the activity of anions and anionic groups of the activators². Resistance to Na₂SO₄ attack is increased by the use of high proportion of slag³.

Hakkineu⁴ studied influence of slag content on the microstructure, permeability and mechanical properties of concrete and observed that microcracks are developed in the alkali activated slag concrete, however, alkali activated slag concrete is very dense and average particle size is smaller than that of ordinary Portland cement concrete. The hardening products of the alkali activated slag are grain like without fibrous and needle like products. The less crack propagation was noticeable in alkali activated slag concrete than that in the Portland cement concrete while carbonation is reported to proceed faster and

deeper in blast furnace slag concrete.

Malolepszy *et al.*⁵ demonstrated that the type of activator played a major role in determining the microstructure and mechanical properties of the slag – alkali binders. Much higher values of compressive strength, bending strength and Young Modulus were obtained in case of water glass activation of slag compared to sodium carbonate activation. The more compact structure of CSH gel and smaller porosity assured the high strength.

There is still insufficient knowledge and conflicting views regarding the inter relationship between the Portland-slag cement properties and various parameters of slag activation.

Considering the scientific importance of Portland-slag cement for its successful application in construction technology, a systematic study on the role and optimal dosage of activators seems absolutely essential in relation to the nature of slag, cement clinker, aggregate and curing techniques.

The present paper focuses the effect of a polyelectrolyte, sodium hexametaphosphate and fixed amount of mineral gypsum as activators on the hydraulic and related properties of Portland-slag cement composition.

Experimental

A control cement clinker corresponding to composition of ordinary Portland cement was first prepared using lime stone (Katni, Madhya Pradesh) and laterite clay (Panchmura, Bankura, West Bengal) as starting materials upon firing at 1450 °C in a muffle furnace for 24 h. Granulated blast furnace slag was collected from Bhilai Steel Plant and mineral gypsum from M/s Calcutta Mineral Supply Corporation, Kolkata. These were used as starting materials for the present study. Base composition for the Portland-slag cement containing relatively high proportion of BF slag was chosen which was produced by intimate co-grinding of 56% (w/w) cement clinker, 40% (w/w) slag and 4% (w/w) gypsum by weight in a ball mill.

Initially Portland-slag cement was characterized by specific surface area and particle size distribution with Malvern Zetasizer using laser beam.

The addition of AR grade sodium hexametaphosphate activator on Portland-slag cement batch was restricted to

0.05–0.30% (w/w) only on the basis of cement. The changes in hydraulic properties of cement mortar which included the measurement of normal consistency, setting times, autoclave expansion and compressive strength against curing period and activator concentration were carried out as per standard specification (IS 455–1976) for each sample. The cubes of 1.0 inch size (cement : sand = 1 : 3) with constant water-cement ratio of 0.4 were prepared by the vibro-casting method in each case. Development of compressive strength after 3 days, 7 days, 28 days and 60 days of hydration of mortar were measured in a hydraulic press. Finally the identification of the hydrated phases formed and nature of bonding on 28 days hydrated products with and without activator was ascertained by DTGA studies. DTG analyses of dried hydrated product were carried out in a manually operated thermobalance upto 700 °C at the heating rate of 10 °C/min for each sample.

Results and discussion

Chemical assay of cement clinker, blast furnace slag and mineral gypsum used as starting materials for the preparation of Portland-slag cement are summarized in Table 1. The microscope analysis of clinker is presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Chemical assay of different starting materials

Component	Clinker (% w/w)	B.F. Slag (% w/w)	Gypsum (% w/w)
SiO ₂	21.40	31.72	6.97
Al ₂ O ₃	5.85	19.03	0.75
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.48	5.10	0.80
CaO	65.64	33.40	25.30
MgO	1.15	7.29	0.93
K ₂ O	0.71	0.91	1.20
Na ₂ O	0.23	0.24	0.86
SO ₃	0.21	2.21	38.50
LOI	0.84	–	25.26
Free lime	1.50	–	–

Table 2. Microscopic analysis of clinker

Phase content (% w/w))				Alite		Belite	
C ₃ S	C ₂ S	C ₃ A + C ₄ AF	Free lime	Size (µm)	Mode	Size (µm)	Mode
55.7	26.5	16.3	1.5	5–70	35–45	5–60	25–35

The major components of blast furnace slag are SiO₂, CaO, MgO, Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ along with small alkali and SO₃ which are also common ingredients in silicate glasses. Moreover, quality coefficient (CaO + MgO + Al₂O₃)/(SiO₂ + TiO₂) for blast furnace slag is observed to be more than unity, thereby possessing better hydraulic activity. The chemical analysis of mineral gypsum indicates it's adequate purity suitable for compilation in Portland-slag cement.

The microscopic analysis of controlled cement clinker shows the presence of greater proportion of C₃S than C₂S along with sufficient C₃A phases.

Physical properties of control cement and Portland-slag cement with 4% gypsum addition are measured and are given in Table 3. The variation of different properties are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

It is evident from Table 3 that 40% substitution of cement clinker by granulated blast furnace slag in Portland-slag cement composition increases of normal consistency of cement. Fig. 1 reveals that both initial and final setting times have increased with incorporation of slag. A little lowering of compressive strength with addition of slag is noticed at very early stage of curing in comparison with that of control cement composition (Fig. 2) which may be attributed to the slower initial rate of slag hydration than that of control clinker. However, during later stage of hydration of Portland-slag cement mortars, significant improvement of compressive strength has been observed yielding somewhat higher values in 28 days and in 60 days when compared with that of control cement mortars respectively. After 60 days of curing in water, highest compressive strength is recorded for the Portland-slag cement mortars which accounts for more than

Table 3. Physical properties of control cement and Portland-slag cement with 4% (w/w) gypsum addition

Parameter	Composition			Normal		Setting time		Compressive strength				Average		
	(% w/w)			Blaine fineness (cm ² /g)	consistency (%)	minutes		(kg/cm ²)				Autoclave expansion (%)	Sp. surface area (m ² /g)	particle size (µm)
	Clinker	Slag	Gypsum			Initial	Final	Days						
Neat clinker	96	-	4	3,071	29.0	90	155	470	584	716	760	0.107	0.1760	23.48
Clinker with slag	56	40	4	3,643	29.5	120	175	338	506	760	797	0.048	0.1860	20.48

Fig. 1. Variation of setting time as a function of additive content.

Fig. 2. Variation of cold crushing strength as a function of curing time.

5% gain than that of control cement mortars (Fig. 2). This may be related to the formation of more hydrated products at the later stages of hydration resulting in micropores filling and compaction of structures of slag cement mortars. High slag content in Portland-slag cement is also found beneficial to major reduction of autoclave expansion (Table 3).

Mainly on the basis of chemical principles, the selection of activators for Portland-slag cement is restricted to gypsum and a polyelectrolyte, calgon only since gypsum can be directly incorporated during large scale production of Portland-slag cement while calgon may be added in solution form during preparation of mortar.

The effect of addition of sodium hexametaphosphate at concentration varying from 0.05 to 0.3% (w/w) on the properties of Portland-slag cement is summarized in Table 4 and Fig. 2.

The analysis of results presented in Table 3 and Fig. 1 reveals that the increasing hexametaphosphate addition from 0.05 to 0.3% (w/w) results in a marked increase of initial and final setting times of Portland-slag cement. The corresponding steady reduction of early strengths at 3 days of hydration compared to that of Portland-slag cement composition without sodium hexametaphosphate, when the strengths on 7 days of curing are considered, the strength development shows an initial upward trend

Table 4. Effect of addition of sodium hexametaphosphate on hydraulic properties of slag cement

Sodium hexametaphosphate % (w/w)	Blaine fineness (cm ² /g)	Setting time (min)		Compressive strength (kg/cm ²)			
		Initial	Final	Days			
				3	7	28	60
0		120	175	388	506	760	797
0.05		215	310	315	510	774	800
0.1	3,643	230	310	310	525	775	868
0.2		270	390	297	482	772	860
0.3		315	455	267	482	770	842
	Max	315	455	388	525	775	868
	Min	120	175	267	482	760	797

reaching a maximum value during 0.1% (w/w) addition of hexametaphosphate but follows a descending result up to the maximum addition of polyelectrolyte. A rapid increase in compressive strength from 7 days to 28 days of curing of Portland-slag cement has been noticed at all percent additions of hexametaphosphate and shows significantly high final strengths. The values are almost identical with each other after 28 days of hydration and obviously higher than that of Portland-slag cement in absence of calgon additive after the same period of hydration.

Thus, as an outcome of the study it is apparent that Portland-slag cement mortars activated with minor dosage of hexametaphosphate (0.1%) is optimum to attain a compressive strength as high as 868 kg/cm² after 60 days of curing. However, a continuous reduction in compressive strength results has been noticed upto the maximum of 0.3% (w/w) addition of polyelectrolyte.

Therefore, 0.1% (w/w) dosage of sodium hexametaphosphate to high slag cement composition effectively balances hydraulic properties of slag cement with respect to the setting times and maximum strength development at both early and final stages of curing respectively. The fluctuation of strength in presence of higher dosage of sodium hexametaphosphate at early period is probably due to the increased formation of impermeable film of polyphosphate ions surrounding the cement particles, thereby hindering the hydration as well as the particle-water interaction particularly during the induction stage.

The film breaks up at later stages of hydration and more exposure of reactive species of Portland-slag cement helps in rapid hydration and leads to formation and growth of hydrated phases. Ultimately, it fills up the micropores of the hydrated structures of Portland-slag cement augmenting better reinforcement.

The identification of hydrated phases formed and evaluation of nature of bonding in Portland-slag cement after 28 days of curing are carried out by DTGA studies. The DTGA curves after 28 days of hydration of Portland-slag cement with and without hexametaphosphate activator have been shown in Fig. 3. DTGA (Fig. 3) reveals three strong endothermic peaks at temperatures 120 °C, 180–200 °C and ~480 °C corresponding to the presence of ettringite (C₃A, 3CaSO₄, 31H₂O), monosulphate (CA, CaSO₄, 11H₂O) and liberated hydrated lime phases respectively. Interestingly, in presence of 0.1% (w/w) hexametaphosphate, higher proportions of ettringite and monosulphate phases are formed and little hydrated lime being liberated as manifested from peak areas of DTGA curves (Fig. 3) for respective batch composition.

The existence of more hydrated lime in hexametaphosphate free Portland-high slag cement mortar after 28 days of curing has been noted whereas Portland-high slag cement containing 0.1% (w/w) hexametaphosphate exhibits the presence of little hydrated free lime during same period of hydration attributing to its *in situ* consumption

Fig. 3. DTGA curves of Portland-slag cement mortar after 28 days of hydration with and without hexametaphosphate addition.

Fig. 4. Powder XRD pattern of polyphosphate ion activated high slag-Portland cement mortar after 28 days of hydration.

through interaction in between the slag and added activator.

The XRD pattern (Fig. 4) of polyphosphate ion activated high slag-Portland cement mortar hydrated for 28 days also confirms the strong presence of ettringite (C_3A , $3CaSO_4$, $31H_2O$), monosulphate (CA , $CaSO_4$, $11H_2O$) and calcium silicate hydrate ($2CaO$, SiO_2 , H_2O) phases combined with tobermorite like gels as minor phases.

Conclusion

(i) Initial slower rate of slag hydration is responsible for slight reduction of compressive strength of slag cement at very early stage of hydration which is offset by the formation of more hydrated product at the later stages of hydration resulting in micropore filling and interlocking structures of cement mortars.

(ii) The slag cement containing 40% (w/w) BF slag exhibited steady increase in compressive strength with increase in curing times for all percentages of hexametaphosphate addition (up to 0.3%) and attained

maximum value of 868 kg/cm^2 after 60 days of curing by incorporating as little as 0.1% (w/w) hexametaphosphate.

(iii) The incorporation of hexametaphosphate to high slag-Portland cement results in a little reduction in strength during early stages of hydration but the ultimate strength appears much more than that of either neat cement clinker or control cement mortar due to enhanced formation of hydrated cement phases and additional hydraulic bond formation.

References

1. S. N. Ghosh, D. M. Joshi, S. Chandra and H. Vaishnav, "Studies on activation of slag cement", Proceedings of 10th ICCI, Sweden, 1997.
2. P. M. Giffard and J. E. Gillot, *Cem. Conc. Res.*, 1996, **26**, 21.
3. R. S. Gollop and H. F. W. Taylor, *Cem. Conc. Res.*, 1996, **26**, 1029.
4. T. Hakkinen, *Cem. Conc. Res.*, 1993, **3**, 518.
5. J. Malolepszy and M. Petri, "High strength slag alkaline binders", 8th ICCI, IV, 1995, 108.